

17 November 2020

Press Release

Accelerating Data Solutions to save LIVES from COVID-19

The consortium of **COVID-X** announces the launch of a unique acceleration program in Europe - a **2-year** initiative that will invest **4 million €** to fast-track to market **30+ European data technology solutions** defeating COVID-19 Challenges, facilitating an innovative stack of AI-driven tools.

COVID-19 pandemic is hitting with force. Europe has passed the threshold of **250,000 deaths** since February 2020. **COVID-X** takes the battle against coronavirus to a new level by bridging the gap between the European digital sector and the healthcare system. The program will **unlock the full capacity of Artificial Intelligence and Data to fight COVID-19**, validating, and scaling up breakthroughs to save lives.

COVID-X will fund **EU Companies** and **Healthcare Providers** to boost data-driven solutions with the power to overcome challenges in Diagnosis, Prognosis, and Follow-up. The funding is invested in products with TRL 7+ and [or in the process of] CE marking, covering two profiles: **single players** (EU Tech SMEs / Start-Ups) validating their solutions at one of COVID-X clinical partners; or **multiplayers** (Tech Provider working with a Healthcare provider that will validate the solution).

The selected projects will join an **Acceleration Program to boost their quick market uptake**. This will include technical support, ethical validation, and business coaching. In addition, participants will have access to the **COVID-X Sandbox**, a one-stop platform to exploit COVID-19 data sources, incorporating general information on data silos, as well as the integration, visualization, and exploratory analysis for easy understanding.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101016065

The program is launching 2 Open Calls and the first Open Call will be launched in early December, with deadline at the end of January 2021.

COVID-X involves a consortium of 10 prominent partners from 7 different countries:

For more information

/covid-x

@TheCovidX

info@covid-x.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101016065